

Study of Serum Magnesium in Bronchial Asthma in Maharashtra Population

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Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Bronchial asthma is a disorder defined by its clinical, physio-pathological characteristics. It has shortness of breath episodes that aggravate at night. It impairs physical and social life. Hypomagnesemia is closely associated with bronchial asthma.

Method: 250 (two hundred fifty) adult bronchial asthma patients and 250 (one hundred) healthy adult groups were studied and compared. In every patient, 2 ml of venous blood was collected to investigate serum magnesium, CBC, ESR, sputum for AFB, and Gram stain for S. mg. were measured by the Elisa kit, chest x-rays were taken, and spirometry was measured to analyse PEFr, FEV, and ECG.

Results: The FEV1 in bronchial asthma patients was 45.78 (\pm 0.36) and 95.42 (\pm 1.24) in control; the t-test was 60.7, and $p < 0.001$. Serum magnesium in bronchial asthma patients had 1.66 (\pm 0.14), and the control group had 2.24 (\pm 0.05); the t-test was 6.10, and $p < 0.41$ (p-value was highly significant).

Conclusion: It is confirmed that if serum magnesium is reduced, it may aggravate bronchoconstriction in bronchial asthma patients, leading to morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: bronchodilation, forced expiratory volume (FEV), serum magnesium, chest x-ray, ELISA kit.

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Introduction

Magnesium is the fourth most abundant cation in the human body and the second most common intracellular cation [1]. Magnesium intervenes in calcium transport mechanisms and intracellular phosphorylation reactions, and so on; it constitutes an important determinant of the contraction and relaxation state of bronchial smooth muscle [2]. Magnesium deficiency is associated with increased contractility of smooth muscle cells. Contractility of bronchial smooth muscle is important in patients with asthma [3]. It is proved that intravenous administration of magnesium sulphate therapy improves pulmonary function and reduces hospital admission in severe bronchial asthma with life-threatening patients [4]. Hence an attempt is made to estimate the level of magnesium sulphate in bronchial asthma patients and compare it with healthy volunteers.

Material and Methods

250 (two hundred fifty) patients regularly visited the Medicine department of JIU's IIMSR Medical College and Noor Hospital, Warudi, Tq-Badnapur Dist -Jalna Maharashtra-431202 were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: The patients were over 18 years old and clinically diagnosed with bronchial

asthma, and they gave consent in writing. No asthma attack at least one week before the study was included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients who are smokers, pregnant, breastfeeding mothers, menopausal or postmenopausal, or have type II DM or bronchopulmonary malignancy. Immune-compromised patients were excluded from the study.

Method: In the present study, 250 (two hundred fifty) bronchial asthma patients are compared with a 250 (two hundred fifty) (healthy) controlled group. The detailed history of every patient's occupation, duration of asthma, dietary habits, and previous medications was noted.

A pulmonary function test was carried out using the spirometry peak expiration flow rate (PEFR), forced expiratory volume (FEV), and FEV/FVC of 25-75% recorded. 2 ml of venous blood was collected from each patient after taking the necessary median cubital vein aseptic precautions. After collecting the blood sample, it was allowed to clot. After half an hour, the blood was centrifuged to separate the serum from the clot. After centrifugation, the serum was stored at minus 20°C in FPP end or F tubes until analysis was done. Serum

magnesium was measured using the spectrophotometric method; other investigations included chest x-rays, complete blood count (CBC), ESR (erythrocyte sedimentation rate), electrocardiography, and sputum for AFB and Gram stains for each patient.

The duration of the study was from October 2023 to November 2024.

Statistical analysis:

The body mass index, spirometric values, and serum magnesium levels were compared in bronchial asthma patients and a controlled group with a t test, and significant results were noted. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software. The ratio of males and females was 2:1.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Comparison of Body Mass Index (BMI) in the bronchial asthma patients and controlled groups: 25.50 (± 0.46) in the bronchial asthma patients and 26.38 (± 0.56) in the controlled group; t-test was 18.7, and p < 0.001 (p-value is highly significant).

Table 2: Comparison of FEV₁ values between bronchial asthma and controlled groups: 45.78 (± 0.36) in the bronchial asthma group and 95.42 (± 60.7) in the controlled group; t-test was 60.7, and p < 0.001 (p-value is highly significant).

Table 3: Comparison of serum magnesium levels in both the bronchial asthma group and the controlled group: 1.66 (± 0.14) in the bronchial asthma group and 2.25 (± 0.05) in the controlled group; the t-test was 6.10, and p < 0.001 (p-value is highly significant).

Table 1: Comparison study of Body Mass Index (BMI) in Bronchial asthma patients and controlled group

Parameter	Bronchial Asthma (250)	Controls (250)	t test	p value
BMI	25.50 (± 0.46)	26.38 (± 0.58)	18.7	P<0.001

Figure 1: Comparison study of Body Mass Index (BMI) in Bronchial asthma patients and controlled group

Table 2: Comparison of FEV₁ values between Bronchial asthma patients and controlled group

Parameter	Bronchial Asthma (250)	Controlled group (250)	t test	p value
FEV ₁	45.78 (± 0.36)	95.42 (± 1.24)	90.7	P<0.001

P<0.001 (p value is highly significant)

Figure 2: Comparison of FEV₁ values between Bronchial asthma patients and controlled group

Table 3: Comparison of Serum Magnesium values between Bronchial asthma patients and controlled group

Particular	Bronchial Asthma (250)	Controlled group (250)	t test	p value
Serum magnum	1.66 (± 0.14)	2.24 (± 0.05)	6.10	P<0.001

P<0.001 (p value is highly significant)

Figure 3: Comparison of Serum Magnesium values between Bronchial asthma patients and controlled group

Discussion

The present study of serum magnesium level in bronchial asthma patients in the Maharashtra population. The body mass index of bronchial asthma patients and the controlled group was compared, and the p-value was highly significant ($p < 0.001$). (Table 1) The FEV1 values between the bronchial asthma and controlled groups were compared: 45.78 (± 0.38) in the bronchial asthma patients group and 95.42 (± 1.24) in the controlled group; the t-test value was 60.7, and $p < 0.001$ (the p-value was highly significant) (Table 2). Serum magnesium level in bronchial asthma patients was 1.66 (± 0.14) and 2.24 (± 0.05) in the controlled group; the t test was 6.10, and $p < 0.001$ (p value was highly significant) (Table 3).

These obtained values were more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6]. Serum magnesium plays a vital role in the pathophysiology of allergic reactions, especially in bronchial asthma [7]. Contraction and dilation of myofibrillar proteins in smooth muscles of the bronchi are due to the phosphorylation and de-phosphorylation processes, which include the enzymes myosin kinase and myosin phosphate.

Myosin kinases are magnesium-dependent, and myosin phosphates are calcium-dependent enzymes. Since magnesium is involved in calcium transport across the cellular membrane, both enzymes are directly or indirectly influenced by magnesium (serum Mg) level [8].

Hence, serum Mg plays a vital role in the contraction and dilatation of the muscles of the bronchial alveoli. Therefore, a reduction in serum Mg level leads to hyperactivity in the bronchial alveoli. Thus, there will be an aggravation of respiratory movement usually observed in bronchial asthma, and there will also be a reduced FEV1 level (Table 2, 3). It was proven that serum Mg level 2 gm is ideal to treat bronchial asthma. Serum Mg is also used as a tocolytic agent for preterm labor, given the I.V. route up to 4-6 g/dl, but continuous infusion may cause major toxicity when serum Mg is at 9 gm/dl and above, causing loss of reflexes, blurred vision, lethargy, muscle weakness, and pulmonary edema [9].

In the case of hypermagnesemia levels, hemodialysis was done to prevent high risks to renal function. Hence, nebulized Mg has proven more efficient to control or relieve episodes of bronchial asthma than an adjacent dosage. Treatment of altered Mg^{++} status depends on the clinical setting and may include the addition of a potassium/ Mg^{++} -sparing drug to an existing diuretic regimen. Serum Mg is a cofactor in over 300 intracellular enzymatic reactions utilizing high-energy phosphate bounds. Magnesium has been implicated in smooth muscle

contraction. Apart from relaxing bronchial smooth muscle, it has calcium channel-blocking properties, inhibition of cholinergic neuromuscular transmission with decreased sensibility to the depolarizing action of acetylcholine, stabilizing the mast cells and T-lymphocytes [10], stimulation of nitric oxide, and prostacyclin.

Summary and Conclusion

The present study of serum Mg in bronchial asthma patients among the Maharashtra population is quite helpful to physicians in treating bronchial asthma with serum Mg as an adjacent dosage for relaxation of hyperactive bronchial alveoli. This study suggests there is a strong relationship between intracellular Mg levels and methacholine bronchial reactivity. Hence, Mg level alterations may play a role in the pathogenesis of bronchial asthma. But this study demands further pathophysiological, genetic, bimolecular, and nutritional studies to shed more light on this subject because the exact intracellular action of serum magnesium on the smooth musculature of the bronchoalveoli is still unclear.

Limitation of study:

Due to the tertiary location of the research center, the small number of patients, and the lack of the latest techniques, we have limited findings and results.

This research work has been approved by the ethical committee of the IIMSR Medical College and Noor Hospital Warudi Badnapur (Tq), Jalna (dist), Maharashtra-431202.

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